

Role of Actors in the Implementation of Minimum Service Standards Policy in the Field of Food Security

(Ministerial Regulation Study No. 65/2010)

Author's Details:

¹**Kus Indarto**-¹ Public Administration, Administrative Sciences Faculty, University of Brawijaya Malang, Indonesia Email : kusindarto@yahoo.com ²**Abdul Hakim**, ²**Tjahjanulin Domai**, ²**Lely Indah Mindarti**
²Public Administration, Administrative Sciences Faculty, University of Brawijaya-Malang, Indonesia
Email : hakimend61@gmail.com, ulinfia@ub.ac.id, indahlelyta@gmail.com

Abstract

Food has always been a problem in poor and developing countries, including Indonesia. In 2013, the highest number of people who were highly vulnerable to food was in West Java, with 8,531,848 people and the lowest was in East Java, with 175,865 people. Meanwhile for East Kalimantan, the population in the very vulnerable category in 2013 was 1,038,490 people. The large number of people who experience food insecurity and are very food insecure encourages the government to gradually reduce this number. An increasingly high food supply is required, given the growing population. The role of actors in the implementation of Ministerial Regulation No. 65/2010 concerning minimum service standards in the field of food security in Kutai Kartanegara Regency, East Kalimantan. The effort to achieve food security is a form of service provided by the government to its people, in other words, it is a public service provided by the government.

This research is a qualitative research with descriptive methods. Data were collected through interviews, documentation and observation. The reason why Kutai Kartanegara Regency was chosen as the research location is because as the largest rice producing district in East Kalimantan Province, there are still many villages that experience food insecurity. In addition, there are also cases of fresh food contaminated with hazardous materials, as well as insufficient food reserves. The results of this study found that, of the seven existing indicators, 5 indicators can be achieved properly. However, indicators of strengthening food reserves and handling food insecurity have not been achieved. Existing targets cannot be achieved. the role of actors in the implementation of food security MSS in Kutai Kartanegara district, has not yet been fully implemented.

Keywords: actor role, implementation, service standards, security, food

INTRODUCTION

East Kalimantan, as one of the provinces in Indonesia, cannot be separated from the problem of food security. This proves that a number of groups in East Kalimantan are pessimistic about the food security program in East Kalimantan that will be achieved. This can be seen from the indication that the rice self-sufficiency program has not yet been realized. Another fact is that East Kalimantan's dependence on rice supplies from Java and Sulawesi is still high, because local farmers have not been able to meet the needs of these regions. On the other hand, a lot of potential agricultural land area continues to shrink, mainly because it is converted into coal mining concessions, it is estimated that at least 4,000 hectares of agricultural land have disappeared (antarakaltim.com, downloaded 16/01/2015, 12:05 WIB)

In an effort to increase food production, the East Kalimantan provincial government has actually launched the Food Estate Program, since 2011. The program was created based on Government Regulation (PP) No.18 Year of 2010 concerning Plant Cultivation Business, which is an umbrella for investing through food estate. According to Syaikat (2010), food estate is a concept of developing food production that is carried out in an integrated manner, including agriculture, plantations and even livestock that are located in a very large area of land (an integrated farming, plantation and livestock zone).

The food estate program is planned to be distributed in 10 districts in East Kalimantan, before finally a number of districts merged into the Province of North Kalimantan (Kaltara). However, the program did not work as expected. The failure of the food estate program in East Kalimantan was due to the district's inability to provide land, because it had already been occupied by coal mining and oil palm plantations. The program was impressed only as rhetoric from the East Kalimantan provincial government. Therefore, the

people's representatives (DPRD) asked the government to prioritize handling land conversion and land rehabilitation to optimize agricultural production. (Prokaltim, 2013)

In relation to efforts to increase food production, the Government of Kutai Kartanegara Regency has enacted a regional regulation (perda) no. 3 Year of 2013 concerning the Protection of Sustainable Agricultural Land. The perda states that the protection of sustainable agricultural land is a system and process in planning and stipulating, developing, utilizing and developing, controlling and supervising food agricultural land and its area in a sustainable manner. Therefore, it is natural that Kutai Kartanegara Regency can produce more rice than other districts in East Kalimantan.

As a manifestation of its success in increasing food production, Kutai Kartanegara Regency has succeeded in becoming the largest rice producing area in East Kalimantan. According to Bappeda Kaltim (2014, p. 201) it is said that 46.37 percent of rice production in East Kalimantan is produced by Kutai Kartanegara Regency. Even for lowland rice, production from Kutai Kartanegara reaches 52.89 percent of all lowland rice in East Kalimantan. Although Kutai Kartanegara Regency is the largest rice producing district in East Kalimantan, there are still many villages that experience food insecurity in this district. This can be seen from research conducted by the Kutai Kartanegara (Kukar) Regional Research Council (DRD). The research shows that there are 40 villages experiencing food insecurity, especially rice commodities. Food security cannot be separated from problems of production, consumption and distribution. It is difficult for the community to buy rice due to its high price, which results in decreased purchasing power. Districts experiencing food insecurity on average are located in the upper Mahakam. Kembang Janggut lacks 2,031 tons of rice per year, Muara Wis 321 tons per year, Muara Muntai 1,131 tons per year and Keanohan experiences a rice shortage of 460 tons per year. Rice to meet the needs of the people in the upper Mahakam was imported from Loa Kulu, Tenggarong and Tenggarong Seberang Districts (korankaltim.com, downloaded in June 2015 at 11:44 WIB)

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Concept of Public Policy

Many public policy concepts are formulated by experts. These concepts differ from one expert to another. This is in line with Abdul Wahab (2008 p.50-51) who states that the concept of public policy in various literatures is interpreted and formulated in various ways. The consequence is that none of the definitions made by experts can be said to be truly satisfactory. This is because the definitions put forward by these experts are influenced by certain problems which the policy analysis expert concerned is concerned with. In addition, the approach or frame of thinking used by each of these experts is also different.

A policy is said to be a public policy, if the policy is related to what is decided by the government. The decision has to do with what the government did and what was not done. Public policy regulates life together, not just individual life. Where public policy will provide more benefits to its indirect users, compared to its direct users.

According to Chocran and Malone (1995, p.1-2), public policy consists of political decisions to implement programs to achieve social goals. These decisions are a consensus of values. When analyzed, public policy consists of an action plan or program and a statement of goals. In other words, it is a map and a destination. These goals show us what we hope to achieve with the policy. The objectives also describe who will be affected by the policy. These public policy programs describe the processes or steps needed to achieve policy objectives. Give us directions for doing so.

2.2. Public Policy Actor

Talking about public policy cannot be separated from the actors who play a role in making public policy. An actor is defined as the person or official involved. According to Agustino (2008 p.29), public policy makers are those who have the legal authority to participate in the formulation up to the determination of public policy. Actors or officials involved in making public policy normatively are legislative, executive, administrative and judges. Where each has a task in making policies that is relatively different from other institutions.

Public policy actors in Indonesia, namely state and government institutions that are authorized to make legislation or policies are:

(1) the People's Consultative Assembly (MPR); (2) the People's Representative Council (DPR); (3) President; (4) Government; (a) President as head of government (central government); (b) the Minister; (c) Non-Departmental Government Agencies; (d) Directorate General (Dirjen); (e) Other State Agencies (Central Bank, BUMN, etc.); (f) Provincial Government; (g) Municipal / Regency Government; (h) Village Head. (5) Provincial Regional Representative Council; (6) Municipal / Regency Representative Council; (7) Village Representative Body. (Agustino, 2008 p. 41-42)

Public policy-making actors can be individuals or groups. In this regard, Howlett and Ramesh, as quoted by Lestari (2010 p. 200), say that public policy actors can be defined as individuals or groups. These actors are involved in certain conditions as a policy subsystem. These actors are divided into five categories, namely:

1. Aparatur who are elected (elected official), namely in the form of the executive and legislature;
2. Appointed official, as assistant to bureaucrats, usually becomes the basic key and central figure in the policy process or policy subsystem;
3. Interest groups, in which the government and politicians often need information presented by interest groups for the sake of policy-making effectiveness or to attack their opposition;
4. Research organizations in the form of universities, expert groups or policy consultants;
5. Mass media, as a crucial network of relationships between the state and society as a media for socialization and communication, reports on problems that are combined between the role of the reporter and the role of active analysis as an advocate for solutions.

Abdul Wahab (2005 p.29), citing Jones's opinion, said that there are at least four groups or types of actors (actors) involved in the policy process, namely the rationalist group, the technical group, the incremental group, and the reformist group. Rationalists behave identically with professional policy planners and analysts and are highly trained in using rational methods. The technician class plays the role of a specialist or expert to handle certain tasks. The incremental group is identified with politicians. Where these politicians tend to be critical but often impatient with the work style of planners and technicians. The reformists want social change.

Thus, public policy actors are those who have the legal authority to participate in the formulation of public policies, up to their enactment. These public policy actors have roles and responsibilities that they must carry out. When these actors can work together and support each other, there will be public policies that provide great benefits to society. Where the interests of the community will be accommodated in public policies taken by the government.

RESEARCH METHOD

The method used is descriptive method. The descriptive method according to Nazir (2003: 54) is a method of examining a group of people, an object, a condition, a system of thought or an event in the present. The purpose of descriptive research is to create descriptions, descriptions or paintings in a systematic, factual and accurate manner regarding the facts, characteristics and relationships between the phenomena being investigated. Furthermore, according to Bungin (2007, pp. 68-69) the qualitative descriptive format focuses on certain units of various phenomena.

Nasution who was later quoted by Rahmat (2009) said that qualitative research analysis was carried out continuously from the beginning to the end of the study. This study uses data analysis techniques such as those developed by Miles and Huberman (2014) which state that the analysis consists of three simultaneous activity lines, namely data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions or verification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Role of actors in the Implementation of Provincial and District / City Minimum Service Standards for Food Security

Efforts to achieve food security are not easy. For this reason, apart from the need for good policies and programs, it requires the involvement of various existing actors.

1. *Role of Community Groups to Manage Community Food Reserves*

Based on the Technical Guidelines for MOA 65/2010, it is said that food reserves include government food reserves and community food reserves. The amount of government food reserves at the provincial level is at least 200 tons equivalent to rice, at the district level a minimum of 100 tons is equivalent to rice.

Meanwhile, the community's food reserves are at least 500 kg equivalent to rice, and at the Neighborhood Association (RT) level at least can meet the needs for 3 months. Government food reserves are managed by the government, while community food reserves are managed by the community.

So the role of community groups managing community food reserves is to manage food barns containing grain which is assistance from the government. They make an agreement with the community about how much interest (profit) must be paid when borrowing and when they must repay the loan. From the results of the interviews conducted, it is known that the benefits that must be paid by the borrowing community vary, depending on their agreement with the management / manager. In addition, the maximum borrowing also varies.

2. *The Indonesia Logistics Bureau (BULOG) as manager of government food reserves*

The government has food reserves which are managed by (Logistics Agency) BULOG to meet the needs of the community. Thus, the role of BULOG is actually to accommodate government food reserves. BULOG tries to protect the rice it stores from being damaged, by rotating or trading it, as long as the food reserves are available, when needed.

3. *Village Food Cadres and PKK (Family Welfare Development)*

That a Village Food Cadre was never formed. PKK plays a lot of roles in the activities carried out by Civil Service, Education and Training Agency (BKPP), including being involved in menu creation competitions, disseminating information on diverse, nutritious and balanced foods. Besides that, it is also in order to utilize the yard by planting vegetables.

4. *College*

Higher education also plays a role in efforts to achieve food security in Kutai Kartanegara Regency. Based on the results of research conducted, the role of universities in the implementation of minimum service standards in the field of food security in Kutai Kartanegara Regency is that universities are also members of the Food Security Council. In the Food Security Council, there is a Working Group Team, which consists of people from the Kutai Kartanegara Regency government, and there is also an Expert Team, which includes elements from universities, namely experts from Mulawarman University and Kutai Kartanegara University. Apart from joining the Food Security Council, another university's role is as a consultant. In this case, the Bogor Agricultural Institute (IPB) acts as a consultant in calculating the score of the Hope Food Pattern.

5. *Food Safety Supervisory Inspector*

This Food Safety Supervisory Inspector is not yet in Kutai Kartanegara Regency. Thus, it can be concluded that the Food Safety Supervisory Inspector does not yet exist. therefore, the expected role also does not exist.

6. *Regional Food Safety Competent Authority Institution (OKKPD)*

Regional Food Safety Competent Authority is an institution that certifies fresh food in the regions. Based on the research results, the Regional Food Safety Competent Authority (OKKPD) for Kutai Kartanegara Regency does not exist, but is located in the province of East Kalimantan. The role of the OKKPD is to certify fresh food producers, namely farmers who produce vegetables.

7. *Regional People's Representative Assembly (DPRD)*

The involvement of DPRD in policy implementation, through planning programs / activities using their aspirations money, in order to solve problems faced by their constituents. And it turns out that in Kutai Kartanegara Regency, there is no use of the aspirations of DPRD members to take part in programs / activities related to food security, so in fact the DPRD in this case is not involved in implementing the minimum service standard policy in the field of food security.

8. *Private*

Regarding the role of the private sector, it can be concluded that the role of the private sector in implementing MSS in the field of food security does not yet exist in Kutai Kartanegara Regency. It has been attempted and but it has not yet been realized.

9. *Civil Social Organizations (NGOs)*

Regarding the role of NGOs, Bp. Bd, "There is no role for NGOs (non-governmental organizations). Thus, the real role of NGOs also does not exist. This NGO is actually part of a Civil Society Organization. Members of civil society organizations that have played a role in implementing the minimum service

standard policy in the field of food security in Kutai Kartanegara Regency are Family Welfare Development (PKK) and Community Group Managing Community Food Reserves. Based on the results of interviews, it can be concluded that the actors involved in implementing the MSS food security policy are: Executive (consisting of agencies and agencies); Civil Society Organizations (consisting of PKK and Community Management of Community Food Reserves); Higher Education (involved as Expert Team in the Food Security Council) and also as a consultant. Then the private sector, but apparently no role has been played.

With regard to actors, Grindle (1980) states that policy implementation is also inseparable from the power, interests and strategies of the actors involved. Actors / stakeholders in the implementation of food security MSS in Kutai Kartanegara District, those involved can be categorized as primary stakeholders and secondary stakeholders. Primary stakeholders are the people of Kutai Kartanegara Regency. Meanwhile, secondary stakeholders are: the Food Security and Extension Agency of Kutai Kartanegara Regency; Department of Agriculture; Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and Medium Micro Enterprises; Forestry Service; Food and Drug Supervisory Agency (BPOM); Food Reserve Management Community; The Indonesia Logistics Bureau (BULOG); Family Welfare Development (PKK); College; Regional Food Safety Competent Authority (OKKPD); Mainstay Farmers and Fishermen Group (KTNA); and the Indonesian Farmer Group Association (HKTI). However, once there are overlapping stakeholders, these stakeholders become the beneficiaries (primary stakeholders), as well as become intermediaries for assistance (secondary stakeholders). The stakeholders are: Food Reserve Management Community; PKK; KTNA and HKTI.

CONCLUSION

The roles of actors in implementing food security MSS in Kutai Kartanegara district include:

- 1) Executive: (agency / service and existing institutions) (play a good role).
- 2) Regional People's Representative Assembly (DPRD), which usually plays a role in policy implementation through programs that use aspiration money, does not exist in the implementation of the food security MSS policy in Kutai Kartanegara Regency) (DPRD does not play a role)
- 3) Private (which usually plays a role through CSR, but apparently does not exist).
- 4) CSOs (civil social organizations), including NGOs (NGOs do not play a role), people managing food barns (playing well), Empowerment of Family Welfare (PKK) (playing well).
- 5) Higher Education (becoming an expert in the Regional Food Security Council, chaired by the Regent), besides that, the university also acts as a consultant in taking fresh vegetable samples to see the pesticide content. As a consultant to calculate the achievement of the expected food pattern score (related to the diversity of food that must be consumed by the community).

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